

Human Capital Development in South Asia: A Comparative Analysis

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this article is to conduct macro level analysis on Human Capital Development in the South Asia countries, such as Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan and Sri Lanka. The Analysis is a comparison of macro level of indicator of Human Capital and improvement of the economy, the research method applied both quantitative and qualitative methods are adapted in describing all the indicators with reference to HCD. In addition, comparative analysis is analysing macro level indicators of HCD made and analytical methods according to the indicators of the South Asia countries. The study applicable since 1990 to 2015, it is an inter-disciplinary in macro aspects of human capital development and also the research is concentrating the group research discoveries on the South Asia countries' human capital development only.

The article presents, for the first time, a comparison of Human Capital Development indices and the approach of the eight nations of South Asia. The Human Capital Index appraises based on current investment on constructing for the future purpose of the nations capital and present result of earlier investment of labour market. The unique feature of the article is a grouping of the analysis of macro level indices with a sound analysis of procedure and intellectual literature. The result provides that in the contemporary human capital competence in the South Asia nations. However, the past two and of half decade, government initiatives of national programme for human capital development, first which are dealing with the health level includes physical and nutrition, second phase it deals educational such as schooling level, higher education, vocational education and training programme and finally which deals about knowledge, level of competencies and earning capacity. The study will assess the gap of Human Capital through the measurements of outcomes Vs inputs of the South Asia countries are arriving the conclusion of human capital development.

"An Investment in Knowledge pays the best interests"

-Benjamin Franklin

1. Introduction

The globalization process an every nation is paying special attention to improving human capital, skill, due to the race or competition in the global platform for improving the economic growth and showing the super power abilities, unless improving human capital, skill formation there will denial of economic growth of the nation, the best people creating best society, the best society building a wealthy economic country. The strong economic country is providing standard life to the people. Comparison needed the developing countries comparing with the developed countries. This fact is important to every nation has realized themselves for measuring the policy of what is right and wrong while implementing the human capital formation. Labour standards are measured at the international level than comparing within the domestic level, such as life standard, wages. Global labour market forces are driving to highly skilled employee in the international level for the negotiation process in the multinational companies.

Human capital development is participating fundamental role for being a rapid economic growth for every country. After so many scholars expressed the concept of presumption (Schultz, 1961) who is the father of human capital was one of the main factors for the growing nation's economy in the industrialized

world. (Romer, 1986) Investment of human capital changes national economic growth. Human capital is measured in the International level measurement of UNDP. The measurements are measuring on the quality of a nation's people. It's referred that in the economic terms more quality of people creating more innovation technology that is knowledge economy which referred intellectual property rights. Men, money, material and methods are completed through the human knowledge in the world. Therefore, the human capital is primary capital for every nation, and every nation has responsibility for improving the human capital. It will also consider as a future pillar of the nation to the next level and next generation it is a cyclical process.

Since, all developed nations are paying more attention to providing all welfare facilities, establishing education institutions, improving literal level, and, other hand, providing subsidies to the people from childhood stage to elderly in the various occasions. The government is providing subsidies and making investment in developing human capital quantity wise except India and China those were in more population countries in this world. It is also very difficulties in managing them at properly due to the surplus of the population and allocation of human resources in various fields. The human beings are from birth to death, referred from formation of children, enriching in the healthy and wealthy of middle level. This process is starting from the personal level, developing through institutional and organization level and finally it ends with strengthening the

social economic level in the nation's level. Particularly in South Asian nations have faced enormous difficulties for uplifting human capital development. Scales fixed by the international organisations.

2. Objective of the Study

This is an inter-disciplinary research broadly focused on human capital development of South Asian countries using trend analysis. Since 1990 to 2015, formally, the international organisations have approached new measurement is to calculate the human capital measures at various dimensions of long and healthy life, knowledge, and a decent standard of life, scales fixed by the United Nation Development Program (UNDP). The Human Development Index (HDI) indicated by life expectancy at birth, expected years of schooling, and GNI per capita income of the Purchasing Power Party (PPP) those are having so many variables such as life expectancy at birth, education, per capita income of GDP, and quality of life.

The research examines the South Asian countries' Human Development Index from 1990 to 2015. The South Asia region compares with the other regions in the world, in addition, comparing within the South Asian countries. Whether the variables met in the international standards or not, and what are the drawbacks are held by the South Asian countries. Further, the assessment is why it is facing such problem by South Asian countries in the country wisely. Finally, a conclusion will help to strengthen the South Asian nations' human capital formation to the comparison between the countries. It will help with the formation of human capital in order to achieve the high skills economy.

3. Meaning of Human Capital Development

Human Capital Development is a gradual development from birth to death developments of physical as well as mentally. The conceptual skill developments are the generation to the next generation or a slow level or drastic level. A country has to allocate human resource, procuring, developing skills and sharing knowledge from one person to others. Further, these are forming through the healthy nutrition, improving skill, feeding knowledge through quality of education, enriching behaviours, attitude and competence level through the training and development process and next level engage them proper field individual earning high-capacity, that will improve the standard of life. It induces to increasing purchasing power parity in the society. Make them an expert in any field, and finally sharing the knowledge to others.

Determinations of human capital are attainment of education level, intelligence and emotional level, attitude and behaviour, innovation, usage of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), and final attainment of social or society skill.

4. Definition of Human Capital

According to the Oxford English Dictionary "the skills the labour force own and is regarded as a resource or asset." It encompasses that investment in people through health, education and training these investments are increasing earnings of money from people.

According to Adam Smith (1777) forth a definition of human capital "The acquisition of... talents during... Education, study, or apprenticeship, costs a real expense, which is capitalised in [a] person. Those talents [are] part of his fortune [and] likewise that of society" (Adam, 1776).

According to Dess & Picken, (1999) define human capital is inseparable from human skills, abilities, knowledge and experience. They were categorised that human capital possessing various skills such as information gathering, processing information, communication, action, knowledge, experience, social interaction, vision on attitude, value and believes.

These are the definitions are emphasis on the general view of importance on growth of economic on each country in the world. Dimensions measured on health, education, training, earnings and expectancy of life. Those are how much an investment is invested in own country's their shares of GDP's by the government to spending for future investment in nations' human capital buildings; such as knowledge capital, innovation, usage of skills, expertise in the field of professional earnings and quality of life.

5. Concept and Theoretical Framework

The human capital measurement is complicated work. Human capital investment is through education, training and development and professional skill and getting output supply to the nations such as the executives, administrators, good leaders, technical professionals, business icons and etc., human capital emerged in the classical economics in 1776, The acquisition talents from human capital and human resource same meaning, the philosopher-economists Adam smith divided human capital in the wealth of nation, human capital is the driving force of economic growth (Smith, 1776), Alfred Marshal defined labour usage ankle that is body or mind, partly or wholly, it may secure income point of view or pleasures derived from the work. Since, the concept has emerged in the early period. (Jacob Mincer, 1958) (H. P. Miller, 1955), the income is discusses distribution of income under three broad occupational groups of employed Blue-collar workers, White-collar, Managers, Professionals and proprietors.

The human capital is divided into two major categories in political economics point of view future investment of human capital in health, education and training; and per capita income of the nation and its role of human capital are supporting national economic growth. (Theodore W. Schultz, 1960) noted that population, education, health and wealth of citizen, (Becker, 1964) the education system is to need a planning model growing economic development. (J. S. Nicholson, 1891) Living capital or human capital, distinguished from the other capital lands, houses and machinery, human being considers as an innovatively intellectual capital growth for an every nation (Stewart, 2001)

Human capital would be indicators such as age, education, education cost, training and development, Profession, seniority and grading (Sveiby, 1997). Measurement of competence of human capital combination of level of education, advanced education, allocation of training, information technology literacy,

invention ability, year of service and value of human knowledge (Stewart, 2001)

Human capital is consisting of people in a country and their skills, efficiency, and productivity. Human capital measures a country's population and their health, education, skill, earning capacity, and the life time. Human capital development is the combination refers in the health avail of pure air, healthy food, proper sanitation, avail of medication provisions and making expenditure on the health aspect. These are the activities, investing education getting benefits in the future.

Human capital considers as a health, education, and forming the children nutritionally and feeding the good healthy food and provides good education to children. This is the primary goal of developed nation, these measurements needed to compare with the developing and under developed countries and third world countries such as health, education, improvement of professional qualification, and good earnings.

The human capital problems are dealing with the labour and it creates social problems. Soviet ideologies have tried to explain the labourers' importance. Labour became capitalists from acquiring knowledge and skills had economic values, later on emergence of technology and innovations created knowledge economy and skill oriented professionals.

The survey of literature review would enable to formulate the theoretical framework human capital development at the international level. Human capital through Human Resource Development (Batras, 2009) research article analysed

internationalized definition and measurements. Every nation has making expenditure from GDP's. The taxations are collecting the general sources, education fund allocation from the education cess. The human capital development through their policies of various categories on education system such as technical, higher education and skill development programme. It is emphasising the knowledge economy status of South Asia Countries. This assessment evaluates the South Asia nation's human capital development, helping to promote the standard of economic growth of human capital.

Increasing the production knowledge, skilled, qualified persons can give their greatest efforts to the economy. Those are promoting an innovation, creativity and new technology, improve the quality of life, human capital formation focuses quality of population, better quality of people will be growth the economic development. Human development is measure of accomplishment of three dimensions of HDI: assessment of health and education, knowledge and quality of life.

International (UNDP) indicators show that average schooling level is 15 years, the highest schooling level is 18 years, beyond that level goes on higher education and professional education, further it depends upon the countries educational policy system. The table I, explains the age wise internationally, human capital investments and outcomes entire life of human beings.

Table I, Worldwide Human Capital Investment on age wise

S. No	Age Category	Investment on HCD details
1	0 -14 Years	Infant mortality rate, Child Health care (Nutrition) public health expenditure, education achievement schooling, and vocational level of institutions spending several years.
2	15-24 Years	Vocational, Higher, technical, professional education and training and development for Professional knowledge, and Information Communication Technology (ICT).
3	25-54 Years	Per Capita Income, Earning capacity is fulfilling economic needs and improving PPP, and standard of living.
4	54 -64 Years	Knowledgeable sources are getting from, well experienced exposures, and standard of living.
5	Above 64 years	Life expectancy of years, prolonged life, and availability health care facilities.

Source: Author accessed from UNDP, 2015.

6. Methodology

The study is conducted trend analysis of two and half decade of the HDI's variables in the South Asia countries, it has two major parts, primarily dealt macro level analysis, comparing to the regional wise, second, dealt the South Asia countries general profiles like population and GDP, index, innovation and growth of the economy. Further, it is analysing South Asia country's three major indicators health, education, and earning level. First, health is measured based on shares of health expenditure percentage of GDP's allocation, and the life expectancy in the years. Second, education expenditure measures on shares in the GDP's allocation, and spending numbers of years in the schooling. Third, it is analysing economic point of view employment to population ratio. Earning capacity is calculated from income index to the GDP. In

additionally, evaluating the Knowledge Economy Index (KEI), it consists of Knowledge Index (KI) and Information Technology Enabled Services (ITES). Finally, it examines the South Asian countries Human Development Index (HDI).

7. Samples and Data Sources

This research sample size chooses from South Asia countries, used expediency sample methods. Measurement and Variables selected from the human capital development of the South Asia countries. Data usages are collected from both primary and secondary data is accessed from International Governmental Organisations (IGOs) and International Non Governmental Organisations (INGOs). Government's expenditure made on shares of health, education, expectancy life and employment from GDP.

Data sources are select from the Central Intelligent Agency (CIA) USA, UNDP, ILO, WHO, World Bank, World Economic Forum, Asian Development Bank, UNICEF and WIPO. Duration of the study period were covered around two and half decades from 1990 to 2015.

8. HDI Comparison in the World

Human Development Index measurement is classified into two categories table-II, shows that Global average level is 62 percentages. The above averages are in the regional wise American continent, Europe and Central Asia, Caribbean. Hence, the below average levels followed, the Middle East and North Africa, South Asia and Sub Saharan Africa. South Asia countries are coming in the sixth place of world level.

Table II, Human Development Index in the world

S. No.	Regional Level of Human Development Index (HDI)	Achieved Percentage of HDI	Shortage Percentage of HDI
1	North America	74	26
2	Western Europe	71	29
3	Eastern Europe and Central Asia	64	36
4	Latin America and the Caribbean	69	31
(Global Average Human Development Index, 62%)			
5	Middle East and North Africa	56	44
6	South Asia	54	46
7	Sub Saharan Africa	53	47

Source: Global Human Capital Index, 2017.

9. Comparative Analysis in Economic Demographics of South Asia

Generally, conduct any research on any nations. First, understand the general condition of the nation, such as population, economic and social condition. Taken calculation of the country's population, GDP, annual growth rates of GDP, expenditure made on health, education and Purchasing Power Party and final measurements on years of life.

Economic, demographic in the South Asia countries table III, shows India has more population and largest democratic country in the world. The Purchasing Power Party is also very

high next to Pakistan. The GDP annual growth rate is very high in Nepal, Bangladesh and India002E

Health expenditure except the Maldives all the countries in the South Asia countries single digital only made, education expenditure highest made by Bhutan. GDP per capital incomes are very high Maldives and Sri Lanka.

Life expectancy the first place achieved by Sri Lanka, in order continues by Maldives, Bangladesh and Bhutan other countries are below the age of seventy years only. Table IV shows that life expectancy and country rank in the first Sri Lanka and the next Maldives. Remaining countries are reducing their citizens' life expectancy.

Table III, Economic, and Demographic of South Asia countries

S. No	Country	Population (in Millions)	GDP Annual Growth rate % (2017)	Health Exp. p. GDP % (2015)	education exp. GDP % (2015)	GDP PPP \$ Billions (2017)	GDP Per capita \$ (2017)	Life of Expectancy (Years) 2017	Life of Expectancy (Country Rank)
1	Afghanistan	34.1	2.5	8.2	3.4	69.510	1,900	51.7	222
2	Bangladesh	161	7.1	2.8	2.2	685.500	4,200	73.4	136
3	Bhutan	0.8	5.9	3.6	7.4	7.011	8,700	70.6	158
4	India	1311.1	6.7	4.7	3.8	9447.000	7,200	68.8	164
5	Maldives	0.4	4.6	13.7	5.7	6.896	19,200	75.8	97
6	Nepal	29.3	7.5	5.8	3.7	78.550	2,700	71	153
7	Pakistan	204.9	5.3	2.6	2.7	1056.000	5,400	68.1	168
8	Sri Lanka	22.4	4.7	3.5	2.2	278.200	13,000	76.9	82

Note: GDP expressed at \$ in Purchasing Power Party (PPP)

Source: Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) USA, (Data are available at later years)

10. Schooling of South Asian Countries

International measurements taken measurement of school minimum level is zero, an average level 15 years and highest in 18 years spending on schooling in the global index measurements. Education is important for consideration of HDI index. Education is how many years, spending in the schooling, based on the schooling, the numbers of years investing, and getting knowledge and education quality acquire by the students. It is strengthening the knowledge for the future

purpose of the students. Education development of Sri Lanka is from 1990 to 2015, 11.3 to 14 years, Except Pakistan every nation of South Asia countries achieved double-digit in the year of 2013. It shows positively increasing an increasing number of years' in schooling investments.

Country code: AFG – Afghanistan, BGD- Bangladesh, BTN – Bhutan, IND – India, MDV- Maldives, NPL- Nepal, PAK- Pakistan, and LKA- Sri Lanka

Table IV. Years of Schooling

S. No	Country	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	AFG	2.6	4.2	5.9	8.1	9.5	9.8	9.9	10	10.1	10.1
2	BGD	5.7	6.6	7.5	8.4	9.4	9.9	10	10	10.2	10.2
3	BTN	5.4	6.4	7.6	9.6	11.9	12.3	12.6	12.5	12.5	12.5
4	IND	7.6	8.2	8.3	9.7	10.8	11.3	11.5	11.6	11.6	11.7
5	MDV	-	8.5	11.8	12	11.8	12.1	12.4	12.7	12.7	12.7
6	NPL	7.5	8.1	9	9.6	12	12.3	12.3	12.4	12.2	12.2
7	PAK	4.6	5	5.4	6.5	7.5	7.6	7.7	7.8	8.1	8.1
8	LKA	11.3	11.9	12.5	13.1	13.6	13.7	13.8	14	14	14

Source: UNESCO, 2015.

The trend is showing from 1990 to 2015, the figure,1 shows Afghanistan in 2.6 years in 10.1, it reaches low-level to a high level within a decade spending number of years of schooling in

the South Asia countries. Pakistan could not able to reach the destinations of the Afghanistan. South Asia countries are developing gradually except by Sri Lanka.

Figure 1, Expected Years of Schooling in South Asia

Source: UNESCO report, 2015.

Sri Lanka is spending 14 years in education; next level is Maldives from 8.5 years in 1995 to 12.7 years in 2015, and Bhutan from 5.4 years in 1990 to 12.5 years in 2015. Nepal is

1990 7.5 years to 12.5 in 2015. Next level is India 7.6 years to 11.7 years spending, and finally Pakistan 4.6 years to 8.1 years, spending almost held last place in South Asia countries.

Table V. Public Health Expenditure

S. No	Countries	1995	2000	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
1	AFG	-	-	0.8	2.9	2.1	2.9	2.6	2.9
2	BGD	1.2	0.9	1	1.1	1	1	0.8	0.8
3	BTN	2.7	5.3	4.2	4.5	4.1	2.7	2.8	2.6
4	IND	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.3	1.4
5	MDV	3.7	5.1	7.1	5.3	5.6	6.5	8.3	10.8
6	NPL	1.4	1.4	1.6	2.9	3.2	2.5	2.2	2.3
7	PAK	0.7	0.6	0.7	1	0.9	1	1	0.9
8	LKA	1.6	1.8	1.9	1.6	1.4	1.2	2.1	2

Source: UNDP report, 2016.

Public Health Expenditure allocated of shares of GDP mentioned table V, up to 2000, Afghanistan data may not available and Maldives only spending on health expenditure 10.8% to 2014 from 3.7% since 1995, new levels of

achievement double-digit shares of GDP in 2014. Pakistan and Bangladesh has spending of health expenditure is declining; other countries are maintaining the gradual percentage share of GDP there is no much deviation.

Figure 2, Public Health Expenditure in South Asia

Source: UNDP report, 2016.

Figure 2 shows, Bhutan has in 1990 2.7% of GDP, suddenly increased the share of GDP to 5.3% in the year of 2000, then maintaining the around 4% GDP up to 2011, after that percentage of contribution has declined. The Maldives are spending more expenses for health expenditure on GDP from 1995 to 2014; next level is Afghanistan spent health care expenses. Pakistan and Bangladesh have spent on health expenditure below one percent of GDP in 2014.

11. Knowledge Economy Index

The index covers five countries from the South Asia region such as Sri Lanka, Nepal, India, Bangladesh and Pakistan other countries are Afghanistan, Bhutan and Maldives data may not available in the Global Human Capital Report 2017.

Table VI. Knowledge Economic Index in South Asia

S. No.	Countries	KEI	KI	EIR	II	EI	ICT	KER
1	Afghanistan	N. A.						
2	Bangladesh	2.05	2.23	1.51	3.94	1.75	1.01	122
3	Bhutan	N. A.						
4	India	4.13	4.31	3.57	8.78	2.26	1.9	91
5	Maldives	N. A.						
6	Nepal	1.58	1.66	1.33	3.06	1.73	1.01	134
7	Pakistan	2.45	2.63	1.93	5.99	1.44	3.6	117
8	Sri Lanka	3.75	3.66	4.04	3.06	4.61	2.8	101

Sources: Data from World Bank Report, 2017

Abbreviations:

KEI : Knowledge Economy Index

KI : Knowledge Index

EIR : Economic Incentive Regime

II : Innovation Index

EI : Education Index

ICT : Information and Communication Technology Index

KER : Knowledge Economic Rank (Country Wise)

N.A. : Data Not Available

Table VII. Knowledge Economy Index (KEI) Indicators

S. No	Indicators	Subjects
1	Economic Incentive Regime (EIR)	Tariff and None tariff barriers, regulatory qualities and rule of law
2	Education Index (EI)	Adult literacy rate, gross secondary enrolment rate and tertiary enrolment rate
3	Innovative Index (II)	Royalty payments and receipts, technical journal articles per million people, patents granted to nationals by the United States Patent and Trademark Office
4	Information and Communication Technology Index (ICT)	Telephones, Computers, Mobile phones and Internet users

Source: World Bank, 2016.

Health and education are major contributions of economic drivers in the recent trends, as far as India earns importing from developed country's business process outsourcing and information communication works. Semi skilled and killed

employees are working in the developed countries majority of people from India, particularly in the USA and UK. Semi and unskilled employees are working in the United Arabic Emirates.

Figure 3, Knowledge Economic Index in South Asia

Source: World Bank, 2016.

Figure 3, India only reached high level KEI, KI, and II Index. Sri Lanka has gradually shown their development all aspects of the Knowledge Economy Index. Other countries are gradually

maintained the Knowledge Economy Index. Table XI has shown the details of the indicators of the Knowledge Economy Index.

Table VIII. Employment to population ratio (% ages 15 and older)

S. No	Countries	1995	2000	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	AFG	46	45.5	46.4	46.1	47.2	47.5	47.7	47.7	47.5
2	BGD	70.6	68.1	63.6	59.5	59.4	59.3	59.3	59.3	59.4
3	BTN	62.3	65.7	69.8	67.4	66.2	64.4	64.3	64.3	64.7
4	IND	58.1	56.4	57.9	53.4	52.7	52	51.9	51.8	51.9
5	MDV	45.1	48	54	58	58.5	59.2	59.8	59.7	59.9
6	NPL	84.2	84	82.2	81.2	80.4	81	80.4	80.4	80.5
7	PAK	46.7	47.3	48.9	51.2	51.1	51	50.7	50.7	51
8	LKA	48.8	52.5	50.6	52.1	52.1	51.3	51.5	49.7	49.3

Source: UNDP report, 2015.

Employment to total population ratio shows the South Asia countries since 1995 to 2015 Afghanistan 46% to 47.5%, Bhutan 64.3% to 64.7%, Maldives 45% to 59.9% and Pakistan 46.7% to 51 and Sri Lanka 48.8% to 49.3% has shown positive aspect of employment for population wise, 46 -47.5. Employment to population ratio have been sinking since, 1995

particularly in Bangladesh from 70.6% to 59.4%, India from 58.1% to 51.9%, and Nepal from 84.2% to 70.5%. Shows that, negative aspect due to over population, the government has neither creating job opportunities nor reducing the level of population.

Figure 4, Employment to Population Ratio in South Asia

Source: UNDP report, 2015.

Figure 4, shows the trend analysis population to employment opportunity from 1995 to 2015 available date in South Asia countries.

Table IX. Income Index to GDP

S. No	Countries	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	AFG	0.458	0.373	0.309	0.374	0.422	0.43	0.441	0.446	0.444	0.442
2	BGD	0.386	0.402	0.426	0.455	0.495	0.502	0.511	0.517	0.523	0.53
3	BTN	0.46	0.485	0.541	0.575	0.622	0.629	0.632	0.635	0.641	0.644
4	IND	0.432	0.455	0.486	0.523	0.57	0.578	0.584	0.592	0.601	0.61
5	MDV	0.527	0.565	0.611	0.641	0.683	0.691	0.692	0.696	0.702	0.701
6	NPL	0.371	0.39	0.412	0.428	0.453	0.457	0.462	0.466	0.473	0.476
7	PAK	0.523	0.532	0.535	0.562	0.574	0.576	0.578	0.582	0.586	0.592
8	LKA	0.543	0.574	0.605	0.629	0.671	0.682	0.693	0.696	0.702	0.707

Source: World Bank report, 2016.

Figure 5, shows the income index to GDP Level, Sri Lanka has the highest level of income index from 1990 to 2015, 0.54 to 0.70, next level is Maldives, from 0.52 to 0.70, next level is Bhutan, and next level is India, other countries are average

only. This is the important measurement for measuring the income level of citizen, income only deciding factors of quality of life. Induce to borrowing capacity for conducting health and dignified life in the society.

Figure 5, Income Index of GDP in South Asia

Source: World Bank report, 2016.

Table X. Life Expectancy Years

The main factors are environmental climate is very important and health aspects are deciding factors are increasing number of years in the natural environment, clean Air, Clean drinking water, naturally cultivated food is very important for life.

S. No	Countries	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015
1	AFG	49.9	53.1	55.1	57	59	59.3	59.7	60	60.4	60.7
2	BGD	58.4	61.9	65.3	68	70.1	70.5	70.8	71.2	71.6	72
3	BTN	52.5	56.4	60.7	64.9	67.9	68.3	68.7	69.1	69.5	69.9
4	IND	57.9	60.4	62.6	64.5	66.5	66.9	67.3	67.6	68	68.3
5	MDV	61.4	65.6	69.9	74.2	76.2	76.3	76.5	76.6	76.8	77
6	NPL	54.3	58.5	62.4	65.5	68	68.4	68.8	69.2	69.6	70
7	PAK	60.1	61.5	62.7	63.9	65.1	65.4	65.7	66	66.2	66.4
8	LKA	69.5	69.3	71	73.9	74.4	74.5	74.6	74.7	74.9	75

Source: World Bank data report, 2015.

Expectancy of life depends on the availability of health facilities in the South Asia countries. Maldives and Sri Lanka are paying more attention to the health care system established in the hospital and primary health centers by the nations; this is

the main reason for extended their citizen's life. However, the South Asia countries are gradually increasing the citizen's expectations of years of life; in the past two and half decade extending the age level almost a decade of life.

Figure 6, Life Expectancy at Number of Years in South Asia

Source: World Bank data report, 2015.

12. Comparisons of Human Development Index in the South Asia Countries

Human Development classified based on the cut of index 0.550 below index are noted on the low-level of human development, 0.550 to 0.699 indices referred the medium level of Human Development, and above 0.700- 0.799 indices referred high level of human development and more than 0.800 indices, that very high level human development. South Asia country is coming under three levels of human development except high human development index.

The Human Development Index is indicating any nation’s life expectancy of birth, expected years of schooling, GNI per capita income is real purchasing power party of human beings of the nations. The human resource balanced way to divide to the

various fields, further the government paying attention to enriching their citizens’ development, spending money for health, education, quality of life or well-being of the human condition and life expectancy.

The HDI shows Table XI, the South Asian countries human development is a high, medium and low-level, HDI index reached a high level by Sri Lanka and Maldives reached high level, India, Bhutan, Bangladesh, Nepal and Pakistan held medium level human development index, and finally Afghanistan held in lower human development index place.

Table XI, South Asia countries’ HDI ranks and its Components

S. No.	Countries	HDI index at value	Life expectancy at Birth (Yrs)	Expected years of Schooling	Mean years of schooling	GNI per capital (PPP \$)	HDI Rank
(Very High Human Development) 0.800 > HDI							
(High Human Development) 0.700 – 0.799 HDI							
1	Sri Lanka	0.766	75.0	14.0	10.9	10,789	72
2	Maldives	0.701	77.0	12.7	6.2	10,383	105
(Medium Human Development) 0.550 – 0.699 HDI							
3	India	0.624	68.3	11.7	6.3	5,663	131
4	Bhutan	0.607	69.9	12.5	3.1	7,081	132
5	Bangladesh	0.579	72.0	10.2	5.2	3,341	139
6	Nepal	0.558	70.0	12.2	4.1	2,337	144
7	Pakistan	0.550	66.4	8.1	5.1	5,031	147
(Low Human Development) < 0.550 HDI							
8	Afghanistan	0.479	60.7	10.1	3.6	1,871	169

Source: Human Development Report, UNDP, (2015)

The Human Development Index is showing from 1990 to 2015, HDI rank is mentioned on the basis of the 2015th calculation HDI, HDI measured by the core aspects of

health, education, income level and expectation of years of human being life, details of explanation has given in the table XI

Table XII, Human Development Index

S. No.	Country Code	1990	1995	2000	2005	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	HDI Rank (2015)
1	LKA	0.626	0.651	0.686	0.718	0.746	0.752	0.757	0.76	0.764	0.766	73
2	MDV	-	0.52	0.587	0.622	0.663	0.675	0.683	0.693	0.701	0.701	105

3	IND	0.428	0.46	0.494	0.536	0.58	0.59	0.599	0.607	0.615	0.624	131
4	BTN	-	-	-	-	0.572	0.581	0.589	0.596	0.604	0.607	132
5	BGD	0.386	0.423	0.468	0.506	0.545	0.557	0.565	0.57	0.575	0.579	139
6	NPL	0.378	0.41	0.446	0.476	0.529	0.538	0.545	0.551	0.555	0.558	144
7	PAK	0.404	0.429	0.45	0.501	0.525	0.529	0.538	0.542	0.548	0.55	147
8	AFG	0.295	0.324	0.34	0.405	0.454	0.463	0.47	0.476	0.479	0.479	169

Source: UNDP report, 2015

Figure 7, HD Index of South Asia

Source: UNDP report, 2015

HD Index figure 7, show that all the South Asian countries are gradually increase the Human Development Index. It shows a positive trend of South Asia countries. Comparing with these countries, Sri Lanka has maintained the top-level of the South Asian countries from 1990 to 2015; the next place follows by Maldives also gradually maintaining a sustainable place next level India has followed by the Maldives. Bhutan, Bangladesh, Pakistan and Nepal has within these countries' trends is ups and downs of HDI level.

13. Summary

Foundations of International organisation are gathering every nation in the global platform of competitiveness of goods and services are establishing one nation to other nations, the recent trend process every nation shows unique from one nation to others, therefore, this process every nation want to create a group of nations based on the available of resources, interests, geographically this resultant an emerging new international organisations based on governmental and non-governmental.

Countries are forming a group for fulfilling their requirements, More than one country is joining by cooperation to facilitating within themselves, and facing the hindrance by the common problem group of countries, in these are the activities of government or non government forming like regional wise, trade wise economic cooperation maintained social justice by all the countries has formed a group for saving themselves the resultant avoiding domination and exploitation of other countries.

International Organisations are approaching new measurements, human capital measurement is so many dimensions, and it is emerging at the level from micro to macro. Such as, person, societal, institutional level, private and public, corporate level according to the needs and necessities crafting

the human capital development. However, internationally accepted and many scholars advised to adopt international human development measures. New approach executes by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) reputed method of Human Development Index (HDI). The measurement is scrutinizing country's human capital development through the health, education, knowledge, and condition of life style. It has so many sub variables are measured, nutritional level, EQ, IG, birth, literacy rate, enrolment on education ratio, schooling, higher, vocational, and professional education. The Earning capacity is GDP to Per capita income, Purchasing Power Party.

Advanced human capital has paid more attending on social capital, gradually developing both quantity and quality wise. Social capital formation has to tough government policy implications. Since, the government is allocation of resources to framing policy for future strong pillars' human beings. Maintaining health data based on the countries, analysing themselves, strength and weakness.

This article is comparing of the HDI regional wise in the world level. Measurements are a combination of macro level analysis of three dimensional measurement of Human Development Index. The result is the first place is North America, the second is Western Europe, the third is Eastern Europe and Central Asia, the fourth place is Latin America and the Caribbean, the fifth place is Middle East and North Africa, the sixth place is South Asian countries and the last is Sub Saharan Africa. In this regional comparison South Asian countries are in the sixth place.

Comparison between the South Asian countries with high human development indices is Sri Lanka and Maldives, medium human development to India, Bhutan, Bangladesh, Nepal and Pakistan. Afghanistan is the end of the place of human development index.

14. Conclusion

South Asia countries except Sri Lanka and Maldives are gradually developed and achieved the human capital development, age wise, earning of income and attainment of education levels are good. The trend analysis shows that next ten years will reach to high human development index by Sri Lanka and Maldives.

Sri Lanka and Maldives are spending by 14 and 12.7 years for spending education. Except Sri Lanka all the South Asia countries spending on education years level is in the year 1990 is very low it attained a good level of education. Index shows, that Pakistan is spending for education several years is very low.

Health expenditure is spent by Maldives is very high level in the South Asia countries. Bhutan was spending more shares of GDP in 1995, gradually it is also declining the GDP level. Bangladesh, Pakistan, and India have to increase health expenditure on GDP compared to developed countries are spending most up to 16.4 % of GDP.

The knowledge index shows only five nations, India is leading to innovative, knowledge index; economic innovative regimes are best achieved. Life expectancy is very high in Maldives and Sri Lanka. Other countries are having less expectancy of life.

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15. Suggestion

South Asia countries have increased the several years for spending on education at least should reach an average level of 15 years. To increase education institutions, higher education and professional education should create at the policy level. Focus on expansion of vocational education, research and development allocation of share on GDP to education shares create several institutions such as health, engineering, science and information technology.

South Asia countries have followed the role model of developing countries, education policy, skill development programme, property rights, and fixation of compensation packages. Provide closer linkage with the investment in education, science and technology and innovations on intellectual, social economic developments, and information technology and establishing Research and development of academic and industries.

The human development indicators could pay attention to education, health information technology system, increasing quantitative as well as qualitative wise institution, such as educational, technological, health aspect.

Concentration should focus on balanced efforts on human development of allocation, procurement, investment. From personal, social and national level building strong human capital development.

